

ETHNOBIOLOGICAL STUDY ON THE USE OF *JATROPHA CURCAS L* AS WARM COMPRESSES IN TRADITIONAL MEDICINE IN KERINCI REGENCY

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Abstract

Jatropha Curcas L is one of the easiest plants in Indonesia. This plant is widely used by one community in Kerinci Regency. Some of the Kerinci's people believe that leaf of *Jatropha Curcas L* can be used to treat fever. But there is no previous research on the utilization of these plants in Kerinci Regency. This study aims to explain the techniques of traditional medicine using *Jatropha Curcas L* and the scientific inquired. The data of this research has collected by in deep interview, observation and discussion of confirmation. The data is the emic data that is adjusted with the result of literature study from several journals. The results show that *Jatropha Curcas L* leaves have substances that are useful in treatments such as flavonoids. It can be used as warm compresses. There are several factors that people believe can influence the treatment results such as leaf selection and leaf usage techniques. The tradition of this treatment is very unique and needs to be preserved, considering only some people understand about this traditional medicine.

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1. Introduction

Kerinci is one of the regencies in Jambi Province. The area which consists of mountains and valleys makes the Kerinci area rich with natural products. In addition, Kerinci is known as an area that has a variety of traditions and cultures that are growing in the community. Almost every region in Kerinci district has different characteristics of culture and tradition. One unique tradition is traditional medicine. Like other regional communities, indigenous people also use plants as a medicine to cure various diseases. Traditional treatments derived from plants or natural are more popular with the community, this is because the prices are cheap and do not cause side effects compared to using drugs from chemicals. The use of traditional medicines for health care and disease disorders is still very much needed. Analysis of chemical components of medicinal plants needs to be intensified to find out the role in the healing process [1]

One of the plants used is *Jatropha Curcas L*. This plant thrives in various places in the Kerinci area. Plants are usually grown in the wild, even in community houses. Many people do not know the benefits of *Jatropha Curcas L*. It caused, this plant is used as a traditional medicine for generations which some people know. It is feared that traditional treatments using this plant will slowly become extinct. The development of modern medicine today can make people forget traditional knowledge slowly.

The leaves of *Jatropha Curcas L* contains substances alkaloids, saponins, tannins, terpenoids, steroids, glycosides, phenolic compounds and flavonoids through ethanol extract [2]. It is one of the plants that contains latex, which is the main secondary. In addition there are secondary metabolites; polyphenols, tannins, and polysaccharides that can inhibit the action of enzymes [3]. It contains many secondary metabolites which are the active compounds. This is evident from the habits of the people who often use this leaves for treating swelling, sprains, bleeding wounds, itching, eczema, and water fleas. *Jatropha Curcas L* leaves is fungicidal or be killed to the fungus *Candida albicans* with the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) at a concentration of 12.5% and fungicidal Minimum Concentration (MFC) can kill at a concentration of 75 %, so it effectively inhibits growth and kills the fungus *Candida albicans* [4].

Based on some of the results of the study it can be seen that the *Jatropha Curcas L* leaves have substances that have the potential to cure disease. Kerinci society itself believes that distance leaves can be used to treat fever. In this study a biology study on the role of castor leaves in traditional medicine will be carried out. In this study the treatment process will be revealed starting from the preparation of tools and materials, steps, and factors that influence the treatment process based on the results of observations. With this research is expected to introduce alternative ways to reduce fever through traditional methods. In addition, the existence of scientific studies on these methods is expected to become a foundation in developing traditional treatment techniques.

2. Method

The research was conducted in Siulak sub-district, Kerinci regency, Jambi Province with a study time of approximately 6 weeks. Tools and materials used: list of questions for selected responses, stationery to record data obtained in the field, and camera for documentation. The objects in this study are the Siulak people of Kerinci Regency.

The study used descriptive method with interviews and identification in the field. Data collection is done by direct communication techniques with selected responses. Interviews were conducted with several community members who had used the treatment technique, both those who treated and those who received treatment. Observations were made by looking directly at the implementation of the treatment as well as documenting each stage of treatment.

3. Result And Discussion

3.1. Result

The people of Siulak utilize *Jatropha* plants based on knowledge about the benefits of medicinal plants that have been passed down from generation to generation. *Jatropha* is used as traditional medicine which is an alternative to treat diseases. The method of treatment performed by the community is very diverse, among others by means of being rubbed, eaten, drunk, smeared, sown, pasted and rubbed. but the treatment technique that will be explained here is the use of castor leaves to reduce heat by being attached and applied to all parts of the body.

Based on the results of direct observations and interviews with treatment and patients who are currently undergoing treatment, the data is obtained in the form of tools and materials needed, details of the treatment process and determinants of treatment success. More details about treatment are as follows:

3.1.1. Tool

- Basin (as a place where the *Jatropha Curcas L* leaves are soaked)
- Glass (as a place of drinking water that will be dipped by jasmine (Melur) flowers)

3.1.2. Material

- 7 sheets of *Jatropha Curcas L* leaves (as a disease / heat transfer medium) (See Figure 1 and 2).
- Jasmine flowers (as an internal medicine to cool the body).
- Frankincense (for burning and smoking).
- Rice, betel leaf and areca nut (as a sign of asking for help to treat someone).

Figure 1. Leaf of *Jatropha Curcas L* before use to warm compresses.

Figure 2. Leaf of *Jatropha Curcas L* after 3 day that has been used to reduced fever (warm compresses).

3.1.3 Treatment process

- The patient asks for help from the medical practitioner by giving the betel leaf or other objects on top of it such as money and food.
- The physicians prepares the tools and materials needed. Such as makes incense fire, arranges distance leaves, and drinking water that has been included in jasmine flowers.
- The physicians start treatment by reading prayers while composing and bloating leaves on the incense fire (see Figure 3).
- The leaves that have been smoked are attached to the body of the sick person, then broomed throughout the body from head to foot (see Figure 4)
- The leaves that have been used are put in water that has been prepared in a container in the form of a basin and put a few grains of rice to see its development after 2 to 3 days.

After the treatment process is complete, 2-3 days the patient will feel the disease has begun to decrease. This is parallel with the many parts of the *Jatropha Curcas L* leaves that has been changed. Indications of patients have gradually become healthy are the number or speed of slowing the color of *Jatropha Curcas L* leaves has been changed. When the color of leaves have begun to change, the disease has begun to move to the leaves. Or in other words the heat in the patient's body has begun to decline. The patient's slow or fast recovery depends on when the color changes in the distance.

Based on interviews, it is known that not only is fever commonly treated with this tradition, other diseases such as measles can also be treated with this method. Some important things that are believed by the public can affect the results of treatment including :

3.1.4 Selection of distance leaves.

The selected leaves are leaves that are about 15-20 cm wide. The number of leaves used was 7 sheets.

3.1.5 Leaf removal techniques

Leaves that have been smoked, rubbed into all parts of the body from head to toe. Especially on the face, leg and arms (3 times swab). But in the abdomen, the leaves are attached to the body for about 5-10 seconds.

Figure 3. Smoking the leaf before use to patient.

Figure 4. The process of warm compresses using *Jatropha Curcas L* leaf.

3.2. Discussion

Kerinci as an area that has a lot of local wisdom. One of them is in the field of traditional medicine. In traditional medicine, people use various natural ingredients. According to most people, with traditional medicine, some diseases will heal faster. But sometimes some treatment methods that are used do not make sense. Because they cannot explain medically the efficacy of the treatment. In this paper the author tries to explain scientifically based on theoretical studies of several research results.

In the Siulak community, Kerinci district, *Jatropha Curcas L* leaves was used to cure fever. Fever is defined as the body's physiological response to diseases mediated by cytokines and is characterized by an increase in body central temperature and immune complex activity. Fever is a state in which T_{eq} is above the normal level of T_b [5]. It occurs when measuring rectal temperature $> 38^{\circ}\text{C}$ (100.4°F) or oral temperature $> 37.8^{\circ}\text{C}$ or axillary temperature $> 37.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ (99°F) [6].

In general, fever occurs due to an increase in heat production that is not offset by the release of body heat. Therefore management of fever is intended to reduce heat production and increase body heat release. Increased body heat discharges can be done by increasing radiation, conduction, convection, and evaporation, including opening thick clothes or blankets and changing them in thin clothes to cause radiation and evaporation [7] [8]. Increasing air flow by increasing ventilation into the house will cause a convection mechanism. In addition, efforts can be made to dilate peripheral blood vessels by wiping the skin with warm water (tepid-sponging) or warm compresses.

Based on the treatment steps it is known that before the leaves are rubbed or affixed to the patient's body, the leaves are first smoked. This causes the leaves to be warm. The warm leaf will function as a warm compress for patients. A warm compress is to coat the surface of the skin with a towel soaked in warm water with a maximum temperature of 43°C [9]. The location of the skin where it compresses is usually on the face, neck and hands. The location of the compressed place is in accordance with what people do in traditional medicine using distance leaves. Warm compresses on the skin can inhibit shivering and the resulting metabolic effects. In addition, warm compresses also induce peripheral vasodilation, thereby increasing body heat

release. Research shows that the combination of antipyretics and warm compresses is more effective than antipyretics, but it also reduces discomfort due to fever symptoms [10].

Based on the patient's healing indicator. The community believes that the indication that the patient has recovered can be seen from the leaf surface area that changes color after soaking for 2-3 days. But this cannot be scientifically indicated. Because the distance leaves whose color changes, can be influenced by other factors. Biologically the leaves that have been soaked, will eventually decay. Although not used as a heat transfer medium

4. Conclusion

Traditional medicine using distance range is one of the local wisdoms developed in Siulak, Kerinci Regency. *Jatropha Curcas L* leaves are used as heat-lowering media. Based on the results and discussion in the previous chapter, it can be concluded that traditional medicine with medium leaf distance is believed by the community to cure diseases, namely reducing heat faster. Physically, the heat reduction experienced by the patient occurs because of a warm compress using the *Jatropha Curcas L* leaves that have been smoked (heated) first. This results in the induction of peripheral vasodilation, thereby increasing body heat. There are several factors that influence the rate of recovery of leaf selection fever and leaf laying techniques. This research is a basic study of heat transfer treatment techniques with medium leaf distance. Several other factors such as radiation, convection and conduction may have an effect on healing fever. It is hoped that in the future there will be an in-depth study of the tradition

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